

Comparison of Thermal Behaviour of Commercial Packages for Power Devices

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Abstract—This paper investigates the thermal performances of four different packages from two different suppliers, both topside and bottom side cooled using 3D CFD simulation. The results show the pros and cons of both solutions.

Keywords—power electronics, package, simulation

I. BACKGROUND

Transistor Outline Lead Less (TOLL) package has been an effective solution for power devices due to its thermal performance for many years. Indeed this package provides low thermal resistance in a small footprint [1]. Recently Infineon proposed an updated package called TO-Leaded Top-side cooling (TOLT), where the chip can dissipate on the top side and not through the Printed Circuit Board (PCB) as TOLL was used [2]. In the same period, Vishay is pushing to adopt two new packages, called PowerPAK® 8x8L [3] and PowerPAK® 8x8LR (reverse) promising similar thermal performances with a smaller footprint.

Since power conversion is one of the most ubiquitous and pervasive applications of power devices in the last years it is natural to look for better solutions, especially if they are promising lower footprints with the same thermal figures.

The aim of this work is to compare four different commercial packages for power devices from two different manufacturers to investigate their thermal behaviour and understand the advantages and drawbacks of different cooling methodologies (i.e., top vs. bottom cooling). Comparisons are made using commercial Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation software (Siemens' FloTherm XT [4]).

The results are useful for the electrical designer, as he/she has to choose between several packages not only based on the package thermal resistance but also on the area occupied and overall thermal performance.

II. METHODOLOGY

The packages under investigation are the following:

1. TOLL (Infineon)
2. TOLT (Infineon)
3. PowerPAK® 8x8L (Vishay)
4. PowerPAK® 8x8LR (Vishay).

TOLL and 8x8 have an exposed thermal pad on the bottom and thus dissipate through the Printed Circuit Board (PCB), whilst TOLT and 8x8R have it on the topside. Figure 1 shows these package drawings.

Figure 1: Package drawings: Infineon TOLL (a) and TOLT (c), Vishay's PowerPAK 8x8 (c) and 8x8R (d).

The comparison focused on package performance, mounting the device models on a simplified PCB designed with Siemens' Xpedition tool and then imported in Flotherm XT.

The models have been shared by both Vishay and Infineon and include all the internal structures of the package.

A. PCB definition

JEDEC [5] defines a standard PCB stack-up for thermal resistance characterization that is a 4-layer (2s2p). The Device Under Test (DUT) has then to be measured in still air in a closed chamber [6]. This setup is different from the one we are interested in, which is a traction inverter for automotive applications. In those cases, the PCB is dissipated with a heatsink and four layers often are not enough for routing necessity and for reducing the Joule heating. For this reason, we chose a different stack-up: 1.6mm thick, 6x 2oz layers. This proved to be for us a good trade-off among current capability, thermal effectiveness, and cost. Indeed, it is the stack-up that we use in our inverters. Substrate characteristics have been maintained constant for all the packages to be evaluated (i.e., the same number of layers, copper thickness, and copper percentage).

On the other side, PCB dimensions are package-dependent, since the reason for adopting a new package is to gain some benefit either in thermal resistance or size. For this reason, we planned to make PCB for testing slightly bigger than the actual footprint, to see the benefit of a package in a realistic use case. The drawings with explicit dimensions are shown in Figure 2. The amount of extra area

beyond recommended footprint has been defined to allow the heat to spread to a larger area [7]. This choice has been confirmed by CFD analysis as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 2: PCB dimensions for Infineon TOLL (a) and TOLT (c), Vishay's PowerPAK 8x8 (c) and 8x8R (d).

Thermal vias are also included and defined to allow good thermal performance, without compromising routing capability and keeping costs reasonable. A good trade-off is a spacing between vias of 1.2 mm [8]. Thermal vias can be realized in different ways and after contacting many PCB manufacturers [9][10][11], we got to these conclusions:

1. Copper-filled vias have the highest thermal conductance, but the process is not so common and thus it is more expensive than traditional solution
2. Thermally conductive resin provides a negligible improvement since the copper plating dominates the conduction but increases the cost significantly
3. Filled and capped via (filled with non-conductive resin) provide the best tradeoff, allowing via-in-pad for the lowest thermal resistance
4. Tented vias, where the hole is only covered by solder mask, are the cheapest solution but do not provide any thermal improvement over standard not-filled via.

For this reason, we opted for filled and capped via.

B. Environment definition

A cold plate is used as a heatsink with a fixed temperature of 65°C as this is a realistic scenario for a traction inverter for automotive applications. Air temperature is kept at the same heatsink value (65°C), using the standard pressure value 101kPa and a heat transfer coefficient with the air of 10 W/m²/K [7]. The target application is a closed system like an Electronic Control Unit (ECU) where there is no significant airflow inside the closed and small case [12].

For the TOLL and 8x8, the Bottom side of the PCB has been interfaced, while the TOLT and 8x8R have been flipped upside-down, thus contacting the package's exposed pad. A Thermal Interface Material (TIM) is interposed

between the device/PCB and the cold-plate. TIM chosen is 300um thick and has a thermal conductivity of 2 W/m/K.

Figure 3: CFD results of simulation with 1.8W. Infineon TOLL (a) and TOLT (c), Vishay's PowerPAK 8x8 (c) and 8x8R (d).

TABLE 1: RESULTS

Value	Unit	TOLL	TOLT	8x8	8x8R
Thermal resistance, junction-to-case, (from the datasheet)	K/W	0.4 [13]	0.4 [14]	0.25 [15]	0.24 [16]
Thermal resistance, junction-to-case, (from our CFD analysis)	K/W	0.5	0.35	0.21	0.25
Thermal resistance, PCB	K/W	0.93	–	1.49	–
Thermal resistance, TIM	K/W	1.46	1.74	1.52	3.16
Thermal resistance, total	K/W	2.89	2.09	3.22	3.41
Effective TIM area	mm ²	102.7	86.2	98.7	47.5
Pad Area	mm ²	49.9	46.5	26.5	26.5
TIM-to-pad area ratio	–	2.1	1.9	3.7	1.8

C. Stimulus definition

Power losses inside each package have been virtualized: instead of using losses calculated from electrical conditions, we opted for setting the same power to be dissipated to fully decouple the package from chip technology any manufacturer can have. The power loss has been initially chosen as 1.8W since it is a power indicative of the operating condition of one of our systems. Then, selected 10W as a rounded value of the peak power in the real application. Regardless, our main metric is thermal resistance which is independent of the absolute power dissipated.

III. RESULTS

Initially, we performed one validation simulation run to check the tool was set correctly. Then all the parameters have been tuned as described above. Figure 3 shows the CFD results for the four packages under exam. The temperature has been acquired by averaging the temperature in significant volumes. These measurement points were: the die, the package/PCB interface, and the PCB/TIM interface. Finally, thermal resistance has been calculated, applying its definition [12]:

$$\theta = \frac{\Delta T}{P} \quad (1)$$

Comparing die and PCB temperatures we can extract thermal resistance for all the packages under investigation and we verified adherence of our results with those expected from the manufacturer datasheets. The results are shown Table 1 and one can see a good match between the thermal resistance declared on the datasheet and the result got from simulating the model. The difference is explained by the setup being different from the standard one.

The table also details the various contributions to the thermal resistance between the die and the heatsink as well as the total one.

There have been some unexpected results: for instance, 8x8 has a smaller junction-to-case resistance (0.25 K/W) than TOLL (0.4 K/W) but the total resistance is higher (3.22 K/W vs 2.98 K/W). This is because 8x8 has a smaller exposed pad (26.5 mm² vs 49.9 mm²), thus the conduction area is smaller,

and finally, PCB and TIM resistances are higher. The same happens also for the 8x8R, where the TIM resistance is much higher than the TOLT due to the smaller pad. Finally, 8x8 and 8x8R have the same pad area and junction-to-case resistance 8x8 has smaller total resistance, even dissipating through the PCB.

Looking at the TIM resistance, we calculated the area through which the heat is flowing, by applying the definition of thermal resistivity:

$$\theta = \frac{1}{\lambda} \cdot \frac{t}{A} \rightarrow A = \frac{1}{\lambda} \cdot \frac{t}{\theta} \quad (2)$$

Where θ is the thermal resistance, λ is the thermal conductivity of the TIM, t is the thickness and A is the area. The TIM-to-pad area ratio indicates the relative increase of TIM conduction area with respect to. the component pad area. From this, we can see how the PCB (in the TOLL and 8x8) has a double effect:

- On one hand, it lies on the heat conduction path, thus increasing the thermal resistance
- On the other hand, the copper planes of the PCB help spreading the heat on a larger area of TIM analysis, the 8x8R is the one for which the heat has been spread least, while 8x8 benefited from large copper planes on the PCB.

In real applications though typically there are space constraints, thus limiting the area of PCB one can dedicate to the single device, while top-side cooled devices can be close to each other without influencing each other temperature.

Indeed, we investigated two PCBs dimensions for the 8x8: a larger one (used in the analysis) that is 13.9x14.2 mm and a smaller one that is 11.6x11.7mm. The smaller one has a junction-to-heatsink thermal resistance of 4.8 K/W, much higher than 3.2 K/W. In Figure 4 it is possible to see how the larger copper planes aid in the dissipation: the region where TIM is hotter than 65°C is where the heat is flowing. Topside cooled devices instead do not need any PCB area to spread the heat. Another benefit of top-side-cooled regards PCB: since it is no more in the conduction path, it can be realized with fewer vias (no thermal vias) and simpler technology (no via in pad), thus reducing its cost.

Figure 4: Comparison between 8x8 with a minimal footprint (left) and larger footprint(right) while dissipating 10W.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We investigated the thermal behaviour of four different packages used for power switches to understand the advantages and drawbacks of these solutions when applied in realistic use cases. We created some virtual PCBs where to host these devices and simulated thermal behaviour when exposed to the same power losses and cooled in the same way. We noticed that even if similar thermal metrics are present for different packages, the actual junction temperature can be different because of the way each device is cooled (either through the top or the bottom). The copper planes on the PCB heavily contribute to spreading the heat, thus reducing the TIM thermal resistance. In top-side-cooled devices where no PCB can spread the heat, the small pad can become a bottleneck and cause high TIM resistance.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Walter, "TO-Leadless: A new Package for High Current High Reliability Applications," Infineon Application Notes. 2013.
- [2] Infineon, "TO-Leaded Topside-Cooled (TOLT) Package Automotive Power MOSFET," Infineon Application Notes. 2021.
- [3] M. Dinc, T. Lohrmann "Measurement and Comparison of Thermal Properties of D2PAK and PowerPAK® 8 x 8L Packages," Vishay Siliconix Application Notes. 2017.
- [4] Siemens, "FloTherm XT" - <https://plm.sw.siemens.com/en-US/simcenter/fluids-thermal-simulation/flotherm-xt/>.
- [5] JEDEC, "High Effective Thermal Conductivity Test Board for Leaded Surface Mount Packages, 1999.
- [6] JEDEC, "JESD51-2A Integrated Circuits Thermalconcerning Environmental Conditions - Natural Convection (Still Air)," 2008.
- [7] J. Adam, "The Printed Circuit Board as a Heat sink." 10.13140/RG.2.2.16806.22083.
- [8] Infineon, "Recommendations for Board Assembly of Infineon Packages with Dual Row Gullwing Leads," 2020.
- [9] Cistelaier, "Cistelaier Technical Capabilities," [Online]. Available: https://www.cistelaier.it/sites/default/files/media/2023-07/202203_cistelaier_technical_capabilities_0.pdf.
- [10] Finline, "Printed Circuit Board (PCB) Capabilities," [Online]. Available: https://www.finline-global.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Finline_Capabilities_Brochure_V3.pdf.
- [11] Serigroup, "Product Range," [Online]. Available: <https://www.serigroup.it/product.php>.
- [12] Nexperia, "AN11261 – RC Thermal Models," Nexperia Application Notes. 2021.
- [13] Vishay, "SQJQ160E Datasheet," [Online]. Available: <https://www.vishay.com/doc/?63059>.
- [14] Vishay, "SQJQ186ER Datasheet," [Online]. Available: <https://www.vishay.com/doc/?66838>.
- [15] Infineon, "IAUS300N08S5N012T Data Sheet," [Online]. Available: https://www.infineon.com/dgdl/Infineon-IAUS300N08S5N012T-DataSheet-v01_00-EN.pdf?fileId=5546d4627617cd8301762e0474f661bb.
- [16] Infineon, "IAUS300N08S5N012 DataSheet," [Online]. Available: https://www.infineon.com/dgdl/Infineon-IAUS300N08S5N012-DataSheet-v01_02-EN.pdf?fileId=5546d462636cc8fb01644081e6ac6348.